

IMPACT OF CHANGE IN LEADERSHIP ON EMPLOYEE ATTITUDINAL SUPPORT IN LGU TANGUB CITY

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Impact of Change in Leadership on Employee Attitudinal Support in LGU Tangub City

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Abstract

This study determined to measure the impact of change in leadership on the attitudinal support of the employees of LGU Tangub in terms of cognitive appraisal, emotional response, and behavioral intention. The researchers employed a descriptive-quantitative research design and a researcher-designed questionnaire as the data collection instrument. The study was conducted in every office of the local government unit of Tangub City. The researchers utilized a sample of 454 respondents in LGU Tangub City. The findings of the study revealed that the emotional response has the highest impact on employee attitudinal support toward change in leadership with a mean of 3.16. Meanwhile, cognitive appraisal has been viewed as the factor with the lowest mean of 3.12. Therefore, the leaders should provide an assessment program to introduce a change and develop it through the interactions between attitudes, beliefs, and feelings of an individual regarding the change. It was found that the government leaders should be focused on the emotions of their employees on how to deal with them, and to inspire them to embrace the changes.

Keywords: *change leadership, cognitive appraisal, emotional response, behavioral intention, attitudinal support*

Introduction

Organizations would experience changes in the environment like a change of leadership, and these would bring about challenges to the organization and employee performance. Some employees could hardly keep up with the changes occurring in the environment. Meanwhile, such changes in the work environment could also happen to the Local Government Units. It has been the practice that every three years, there will be a local election of every city and municipality, and whoever is elected as the mayor and other city/municipal officials will take their responsibilities as head of various departments and divisions. It is of great concern if the mayor is elected for the first time and will take over the seat of the outgoing mayor and officials who serve for long years. With this change of leadership, probably the employees' attitudinal support would be affected.

According to Burke (2017), organizational settings are continually changing, and these changes have an impact on how well an organization can operate and survive.

However, it can be difficult for the organization to keep up with changes in its environment. With this, when leaders promote change, they should engage followers or employees and should shape their attitudinal support (Berson, 2019). Onyeneke and Abe (2021) suggested that to be able to inspire favorable attitudes among the employees regarding change, leaders or decision-makers should motivate employees by collaborating with them, and they should get involved in decision-making.

The City Government of Tangub has a new set of leaders, from the city Mayor, and vice mayor, down to city councilors. The new leaders exhibit various leadership styles which could somehow greatly affect the attitudinal support of the employees. Onyeneke and Abe (2021) stated that employees are challenged in terms of their behavioral, emotional, and cognitive responses to change. This would not just affect the employee behavior, but also the organizational performance.

Now that these leaders have already assumed their position, it is important for these leaders to be well-informed on the possible factors of employee attitude will support their leadership plans. Thus, based on this challenge, the new leader should propose interventions to convince the employees' attitude to embrace the changes for the benefit of the organization.

The researchers are determined to measure the impact of change in leadership on the attitudinal support of the employees of LGU Tangub in terms of cognitive appraisal, emotional response, and behavioral response. The researchers will also determine which among the attitudinal factors has a high impact towards change in leadership. Researchers viewed this field of study as essential to determine what factors that need attention to ensure service delivery among employees, as their attitude may affect their job performance as civil servants. Based on the findings, the researchers will propose a recommendation on how to better manage change initiatives successfully.

Research Questions

This study is primarily conducted to measure the impact of the change in leadership on the attitudinal support of the employees in the Local Government Unit of Tangub City. Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the impact of change leadership on the attitudinal support of employees in LGU Tangub City in terms of:
 - 1.1. cognitive appraisal;
 - 1.2. emotional response; and
 - 1.3. behavioral intention?
2. Which among the factors of attitudinal support of employees has a highest impact towards change in leadership?

Literature Review

Change Leadership

Burns (1978), which stated that the concept of transformative leadership is a great help between leaders and subordinates to boost and advance motivation and enthusiasm. Moreover, this study will utilize factors of change in leadership such as cognitive appraisal, emotional response, and behavioral intention. These ideas will help elaborate on the objectives of this study.

According to Ghavifekr and Adewale (2019), change in leadership is challenging for many businesses to implement because it needs leaders who have the ability to use an appropriate change-oriented style in leading their organizations. It is a management approach that also emphasizes the value of development and adaptability within an organization (Metcalf, 2023). Furthermore, Carter (2020) noted that successful organizations require effective leadership, which frequently entails accepting change. As a result, leaders should be in charge of inspiring staff to have a positive impact on an organization's response to change.

Employee Attitudes towards Change

Managing employee attitudes towards change in leadership can significantly impact task outcomes. For instance, resistance to change may hinder advancement or even jeopardize the job entirely if an employee's attitudes are overwhelmingly negative. According to Arifin (2019), making changes in the organization is not easy because it involves many parties and considerations. One of the things that need to be considered in a change of leadership is the employee's attitude towards changes. Added by Lombardo (2021), change will undoubtedly have an impact on both kinds of relationships. There are some workers who value their ties with coworkers and leaders on both a social and professional level. Stated by Bouckennooghe (2019), positive employee attitudes toward change can be shown by the readiness and openness of the employees to accept change, while negative attitudes toward change can be seen from their resistance and cynicism about change. In the study of Singh & Gupta (2019), they mentioned that employees who have a positive attitude towards change are employees who can be relied on, while employees with a negative attitude towards change will hinder the development of the organization. It is important to understand why employee attitude matters in a change of leadership. Employees' attitudes and mindsets, after all, ripple out and impact other areas of the organization.

Cognitive Appraisal

Based on Junker et al. (2021), dealing with occupational stress and its implications in today's modern workplace is a top priority for both individuals and organizations. Hancock (2022) shared that in a work-related setting, how employees respond to an event or situation depends on how they interpret the demands they are facing, which is known as cognitive appraisal. Moreover, the change involves the emotions of the employees as they feel uncertain post-change scenarios and in such times, leaders' assurance is mandatory to pull them up with the motivation to change (Imran & Iqbal, 2021). Leadership change helps shape employees' beliefs and understandings of the change in the workplace, and it can affect the employees' motivation regarding their decision to put effort into a certain action.

Emotional Response

Mentioned by LaMarsh (2021), people within an organization experienced a change in which the employees and leaders may feel personal loss, or emotionally identify their ability to meet any new expectations that lead to conflict with the reactions of the emotional phases that employees go through during change. Rubin & St-Aubin (2020) also shared that the emotional response are only natural, most especially if there is a change in the organization's practices. This will regulate to manage the employees' emotions that contribute success, not to hinder it. Furthermore, Ahmed (2020) supported that the emotions of employees sometimes feel frustrated regarding the working environment amid leadership change. Lastly, employees disregard the insecurity they feel amid the change of leadership.

Employees Behavioral Intention

Ridner (2022) describe behavioral intention as the way in which employees respond to specific circumstances or situations in the workplace, particularly in a change of leadership in a working environment. However, Wickford (2021) added that organizational changes can also affect the behavior and performance of the employees. He further discussed that it may affect the project outcomes that results in distrust, resentment, resistance, and poorer project outcomes. When organizational change occurs, employee behavior and attitudes regarding a change can drastically affect change efforts. The behavioral intention of them may cause an individual to resist change in an organization like fear of the unknown, fear of failure, fear of loss, disruption of relationships, and internal politics (Lombardo, 2021). Furthermore, Desjardins (2017) said that some of the employees' behavior are unable to participate in discussions in the workplace due to a change of leadership. With this, new leaders should support the new structure in discussions and know how to handle employee's behavior.

Methodology

Respondents

The researchers selected the job order and regular employees of LGU Tangub. The total population for the permanent employees of LGU is 350 and 906 for job order. The researchers used the Raosoft Calculator with (95%) ninety-five percent level of confidence in

getting the sample size. Therefore, the result for permanent employees is 184 and for job order 270. The overall total that the researchers considered is 454 respondents both on permanent and job order. And then, it is proportionally allocated to different offices of LGU Tangub. Moreover, by getting the number of representatives in every offices the researchers used Pro Rate calculation.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study*

Offices	<i>N</i>		<i>n</i>	
	<i>Permanent</i>	<i>Permanent</i>	<i>Job Order</i>	<i>Job Order</i>
City Accountant's Office	12	6	9	3
City Agriculture's Office	20	11	30	9
City Assessor's Office	6	3	5	2
City Budget Office	5	2	2	1
City Civil Registrar's Office	6	3	5	2
City Council's Office	14	7	23	7
City Engineer's Office	52	27	119	35
City Health Office	20	11	18	5
City Mayor's Office	58	31	405	119
City Planning and Development Office	16	9	2	1
City Social Welfare and Development Office	7	4	10	3
City Treasurer's Office	33	17	12	4
Public Market Office	20	11	25	7
Gov. Alfonso D. Tan College	66	36	149	43
General Services Office	5	2	79	23
Office of the Building Official	3	1	0	0
Human Resource and Development Management	3	1	0	0
Office of the City Administrator	0	0	1	1
Tangub City Anti-Drug Abuse Office	3	1	8	3
Office of the City Legal Officer	0	0	2	1
City Veterinary Services Office	1	1	2	1
Total	350	184	906	270

Instrument

To attain the purpose of this study, the researchers utilized a researcher-designed questionnaire which contains three factors namely, cognitive appraisal, emotional response, and behavioral intention. The instrument undergoes content validation with three experts in the fields of psychology, political science, and management. Each factor consists of five indicators. The questionnaire consisted of fifteen (15) 4-point Likert scale items to measure the impact of the change in leadership on the attitudinal support of the employees of Local Government Unit of Tangub City. This tool was used by the researchers to get or generate answers from the selected employees in LGU Tangub City.

Procedure

Before the distribution of the validated instruments, the researchers make a letter of permission signed by the research instructor, adviser, and the dean of the Institute of Business and Financial Services of Gov. Alfonso D. Tan College (GADTC). The researchers addressed the letter to the City Mayor and the respondents asking for approval to conduct the study. After the permission was approved, the researchers personally distributed the survey questionnaire to the respondents. The questionnaire included validated scales to measure the impact of the change in leadership on the attitudinal support of the employees of Local Government Unit of Tangub City. After the survey, the researchers retrieved the data, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted it statistically.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researchers used a survey questionnaire of a 4-point Likert scale. The researchers carefully analyzed the collected data to extract meaningful findings and address the research objectives. Frequency count, percentage distribution, and weighted mean were the statistical tools used to come up with appropriate analysis and interpretation of the data gathered. The researchers used weighted mean to interpret the average response of the respondents of each indicator presented in the tool. Carter (2010) stated that the weighted mean involves multiplying each data point in a set by a value that is determined by some characteristic of whatever contributed to the point. The mean is calculated by adding the scores together and then dividing by the number of scores added.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers followed ethical principles and guidelines throughout the study. The researchers would not reveal the respondents' confidentiality to anybody. Before the start of the dissemination of the questionnaire, the researchers would obtain a written informed consent form from the respondents. It would emphasize that the researchers used the data gathered from the questionnaire for academic purposes only. The researchers assured the respondents that the information in the instrument strictly confidential. The researchers also maintain the anonymity of their identities.

Results and Discussion

This section shows the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered by the researchers.

Table 2. Respondents' Responses based on the Impact of Change in Leadership of LGU Tangub in terms of Cognitive Appraisal

<i>Indicators</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1.	Leadership change affects our motivation regarding our decision to put effort into a certain action.	3.26	Strongly Agree
2.	Leadership change helps shape our beliefs and understandings of the change in the workplace.	3.22	Agree
3.	The new leaders include us in an organization in the decision-making process	3.12	Agree
4.	I am willing to make significant contribution to the change.	2.99	Agree
5.	I emphasize the value of development and adaptability in an organization.	2.98	Agree
Grand Mean		3.12	Agree

Table 2 shows the respondent's responses to the impact of change in leadership on employee attitudinal support in LGU Tangub in terms of emotional response. The highest mean is 3.27 indicates that the respondents strongly agree that sometimes they feel frustrated regarding the working environment amid leadership change. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.09 reveals that the respondents agree. Generally, the grand mean of 3.16 implies that the indicators of the impact of change in leadership on employee attitudinal support in LGU Tangub in terms of emotional response is high.

According to Munir and Sarwat (2022), the impact of cognitive appraisal of organizational change focuses on the individual's positive and negative reactions towards the leadership change. Organizational change affects individual well-being and performance because it shapes the belief and understanding of the change which leads to several reactions. Khaw et al. (2022) shared that a reaction towards a change in cognitive responses is based on an adaption and comprehensive understanding of either positive or negative reactions of how individuals react towards a change. It largely depends on how the leaders introduce a change developed through the interactions between attitudes, beliefs, and feelings of an individual regarding the change.

Table 3. Respondents' Responses based on the Impact of Change in Leadership of LGU Tangub in terms of Emotional Response

<i>Indicators</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1.	I sometimes feel frustrated regarding the working environment amid leadership change.	3.27	Strongly Agree
2.	I support the change of leadership in the working environment.	3.17	Agree
3.	I disregard the insecurity I feel amid the change of leadership.	3.13	Agree
4.	I am optimistic about responding to the change of leadership in an organization.	3.11	Agree
5.	I am confident to work amid the change of leadership in the working environment.	3.09	Agree
Grand Mean		3.16	Agree

Table 3 shows the respondent's responses to the impact of change in leadership on employee attitudinal support in LGU Tangub in terms of emotional response. The highest mean of 3.27 indicates that the respondents strongly agree that sometimes they feel frustrated regarding the working environment amid leadership change. Meanwhile, the lowest mean of 3.09 revealed that the respondents agree that they are confident to work amid the change of leadership in the working environment. Generally, the grand mean of 3.16 implies that the impact of change in leadership on the employee's attitudinal support in terms of emotional response is high.

Wan et al. (2022) stated that employees' emotions have an important effect on their job performance which can be influenced by the leaders on how they introduce the change. It validates the understanding of the influence mechanism and emotional leadership on subordinates. Wang and Kebede (2020) said that employees have different reactions to change since they have different personal experiences, motivation levels, characteristics, and behavior models. The employees' responses are based on the different perceptions of employees regarding self-confidence in learning and development, organizational support, and trust in management.

Table 4. Respondents' Responses based on the Impact of Change in Leadership of LGU Tangub in terms of Behavioral Intention

<i>Indicators</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1.	I feel able to participate in discussions in the workplace.	3.24	Agree
2.	I accept the new leaders of an organization to be able to meet the goal of an organization.	3.22	Agree
3.	I support the new structure in discussions and the support of the future team leads.	3.18	Agree
4.	I have open resistance to organizational changes in discussions.	3.15	Agree
5.	I can handle the distress feeling in the workplace amid leadership changes.	2.95	Agree
Grand Mean		3.15	Agree

Table 4 shows the respondents' responses to the impact of change in leadership on employee attitudinal support in LGU Tangub in terms of behavioral intention. All the indicators are agreed by the respondents. Generally, the grand mean of 3.15 which implies that the indicators of the impact of change in leadership on employee attitudinal support in LGU Tangub in terms of behavioral intention is high. Engida et al. (2022), emphasized that the impact of change leadership can affect the behaviors of employees regarding their readiness to change. Some public organizations focus on individual behaviors that contribute to the success or failure of change implementations. Ma and Tang (2022) have found that for individual teams, inclusive leadership has positive effects on employees'

behavior and performance. Leaders should have the willingness to listen carefully to the ideas of subordinates as well as praise employees that perform excellently to achieve innovative behaviors of employees.

Table 5. *Summary of Respondents' Responses on the Impact of Change in Leadership*

<i>Factor</i>	<i>Grand Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Emotional Response	3.16	Agree
Behavioral Intention	3.15	Agree
Cognitive Appraisal	3.12	Agree

The table above depicts the summary of respondents' responses towards the impact of change in leadership at LGU Tangub. It can be seen that the emotional response factor towards employee attitudinal support of change in leadership has the highest mean of 3.16. Among all the factors, emotional response has a highest impact on change in leadership.

Hale (2023) stated that being leaders should be a model to influence humans to act in ways that drive to have unity in organizations and be conscious of their model of behavioral change. Leaders should be human experts regarding the emotions and behaviors of every individual to be more optimistic and effective leaders with good character and the ability to lead their constituents. In addition, Walk (2022) shared that leaders are not always initiating change but rather executing it. Leadership is considered an important factor for the successful implementation of organizational change especially if they know how to interact with the different emotions and behaviors of employees.

Furthermore, Onyoneke and Abe (2022), emphasized that change in leadership plays an important role in implementing changes that are planned and it is about emotional responses that focus on employees' feelings regarding the change. It can also affect the behaviors of employees that shape the attitudinal responses to change which emphasizes the value of development and adaptability in an organization.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the researchers concluded that emotional response was revealed as a highly impacted factor towards change in leadership, which was strongly agreed by the respondents. This means that the emotional response of LGU Tangub employees is more affected by the change in leadership. It was found out that the newly elected LGU leaders should be focused on the emotions of their employees on how to deal with them to inspire and embrace the changes for the benefit and development of the organization. Therefore, it implies that the emotional response of employees has a significant impact on the change in leadership.

Based on the results, findings and conclusions, researchers suggest the following recommendations. First, the Local Government Unit (LGU) of Tangub City may provide activities that could enhance the relationship of their employees such as conducting team building or capability building to emphasize the value of development and adaptability in an organization. Second, employees may be able to provide support and remain motivated for their work and carry out objectives to accept and embrace the changes despite their personal and professional purposes. Third, the Human Resource Management Office (HRMO) of the local government unit may provide consultation programs to hear the suggestions, comments, or feedback of the employees regarding the change. Fourth, Gov. Alfonso D. Tan College may shape their attitudinal support to the LGU officials to collaborate with them and prioritize the development of their personnel to improve their performance. Lastly, future researchers can consider the conduct of further assessments about the impact of change in leadership with the topic "Effects of Change Leadership on Employee's Readiness to Change".

References

- Ahmed, A. (2022). Employee Reactions to Organizational Change. <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/employee-reactions-organizational-change-17732.html>
- Arifin, K. (2020b). Factors Influencing Employee Attitudes Toward Organizational Change: Literature Review. Proceedings of the 5th ASEAN Conference on Psychology, Counselling, and Humanities (ACPCH 2019). <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.200120.039>
- Bhandari, P. (2022). What is Quantitative Research?. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/quantitative-research/>
- Berson, Y. (2019). Leaders' Impact on Organizational Change: Bridging Theoretical and Methodological Chasms. *Academy of Management Annals*, 13(1), pp.272- 307. <https://doi/10.5465/annals.2016.0138>
- Bhandari, P. (2022). What is Quantitative Research?. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/quantitative-research/>
- Bouckenooghe, D. (2019). Change Recipients' Attitudes Toward Change: A Review Study. *Vlerick Leuven Gent Working Paper Series*, 1–35. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/vlg/vlgwps/2009-14.html>
- Burke, W.W. (2017), *Organization Change: Theory and Practice*, 5th ed., Sage Publications, Los Angeles. <https://www.vitalsource.com/products/organization-change-theory-and-practice-w-warner-burke-v9781506378770>
- Burns, J.M. (1978). Transformational Leadership Theory. <https://studiousguy.com/burns-transformational-leadership-theory/>

- Carter, J. (2020). The Role Of Leadership in Organizational Change. <https://www.modus-group.com/the-role-of-leadership-in-organizational-change/>
- Carter, D. (2010). Weighted Mean. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/mathematics/weighted-mean>
- Desjardins, C. (2017). Cognitive-emotive Change Management. <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/175338/1/18133-71729-1-PB.pdf>
- Engida, Z. M., Alemu, A. E. & Mulugeta, M. A. (2022). The Effect of Change Leadership on Employees' Readiness to Change: the Mediating Role of Organizational Culture. <https://fbj.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s43093-022-00148-2>
- George, D., & Mallery, P. (2003). SPSS for Windows step by step: A simple guide and reference. 11.0 update (4th ed.). Boston: Allyn & Bacon
- Ghavifekr, S., & Adewale, A.S. (2019). Can Change Leadership Impact on Staff Organizational Citizenship Behavior? <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/HEED-08-20190040/full/html>
- Hancock, P. (2022). The Cognitive Self. <https://opentextbc.ca/socialpsychology/chapter/the-cognitive-self-the-selfconcept/>
- Hale, J. (2023). The Most Important Leadership Skill For 2023. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbescoachescouncil/2023/02/17/the-most-important-leadership-skill-for-2023/?sh=27711fa0403f>
- Imran, M. K. & Iqbal, S. M. J. (2021). How Change Leadership Affects Change Adaptability? Investigating the Moderated Mediation Effect of Cognitive Resistance and Change Efficacy. <http://hdl.handle.net/10419/233769>
- Junker, S., Pömmer, M., & Traut-Mattausch, E. (2021). The Impact of Cognitive-Behavioural Stress Management Coaching on Changes in Cognitive Appraisal and the Stress Response: a field experiment. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17521882.2020.1831563>
- Khaw, K. W., Atshan, N., Alnoor, A., Al-Abrow, H., Ganesan, Y. & Tiberius, V. (2022). Reactions Towards Organizational Change: A Systematic Literature Review. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12144-022-03070-6>
- LaMarsh, G. (2021). The 7 Emotional Phases Employees go Through During Change. <https://insights.lamarsh.com/the-7-emotional-phases-employees-go-through-during-change>
- Lombardo, J. (2021). Employee Behavior & Attitudes During Organizational Change - Video & Lesson Transcript. <https://study.com/academy/lesson/employee-behavior-attitudes-during-organizational-change.html>
- Ma, Q. & Tang, N. (2022). Too Much of a Good Thing: the Curvilinear Relation Between Inclusive Leadership and Team Innovative Behaviors. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10490-022-09862-5>
- Metcalf, C. (2023). Leadership During Change: How To Be a Great Change Leader. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/what-is-change-leadership>
- Munir, M. A. & Nosheen Sarwata, N. (2022). Cognitive Appraisal of Organizational Change and Psychological Well-Being: The Mediating Role of Goal Congruence. <https://real.spcrd.org/index.php/real/article/view/221/217>
- Onyeneke, G.B. & Abe, T. (2021). The Effect of Change Leadership on Employee Attitudinal Support for Planned Organizational Change. <https://eprints.lib.hokudai.ac.jp/dspace/bitstream/2115/83114/1/HUSCAP98106.pdf>
- Ridner, J. (2022). Effective Strategies for Working with Problem Employees. <https://www.shrm.org/resourcesandtools/hr-topics/employee-relations/pages/strategies-for-working-with-problem-employees.aspx>
- Robins, A. & St-Aubin, N. (2021). Managing Emotions in the Workplace. <https://officevibe.com/blog/managing-emotions-in-the-workplace>
- Singh, A., & R. P. Gupta. (2019). A Research Paper on the Employees Attitude Towards Organizational Change. Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences, 15(2), 44–47. <https://doi.org/10.9790/0853-152124447>
- Walk, M. (2023). Leaders As change Executors: The Impact of Leader Attitudes to Change and Change-Specific Support on Followers. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0263237322000020>
- Wan, J., Pan, K. T., Yuan Peng, Y., and Ling qiang Meng, L. Q. (2022). The Impact of Emotional Leadership on Subordinates' Job Performance: Mediation of Positive Emotions and Moderation of Susceptibility to Positive Emotions. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.917287/full>
- Wang, A. & Kebede, S. (2020). Assessing Employees' Reactions to Organizational Change. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation.aspx?paperid=102259>
- Wickford, H. (2019). Negative Impact of Organizational Change on Employees. <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/negative-impact->

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